

THE ASSESSMENT OF GRASSLANDS PRODUCTIVITY OF THE LEAOTA MOUNTAINS AND THE WESTERN SIDE OF THE BUCEGI MOUNTAINS

Teodor MARUȘCA^{1*}, Monica NEBLEA² and Monica A. TOD¹

¹ Brașov Grassland Research-Development Institute, Strada Cucului no. 5, 500128, Brașov

² University of Pitești, 1 Târgul din Vale Street, 110040, Pitești

*Corresponding author: maruscat@yahoo.com

Abstract

The permanent grasslands of the Leaota Mountains and the western side of the Bucegi Mountains located at 700-2130 m altitude from a phytosociological point of view belong to the Juncetea trifidi, Nardo-Calunetea, Seslerietea albicantis and Molinio-Arrhenatheretea classes, with 4 orders, 7 alliances and 9 plant associations. Vegetation coverage was on average 76% and the number of cormophyte species in reliefs was 44, being quite high. The participation of species with forage value in the 9 associations was 31%, quite low, with a poor pastoral value (17.8) and low production of green mass (1.7 t/ha). The most valuable association was Scorzonero rosae - Festucetum nigricantis with 41.2 (average) pastoral value and 7.52 t/ha (middle) green mass. Productions of 2-3 t/ha green mass are achieved in the associations Asperulo capitatae- Seslerietum rigidae and Seslerio haynaldianae-Caricetum sempervirentis, in the remaining 6 associations it was evaluated below one ton per hectare. Finally, at the phytosociological level, an average of 1020 liters of milk/ha was evaluated in 95 days of grazing season with variations from 200 l/ha at Molinietalia to 2040 l/ha at Seslerietalia albicantis. The productivity of the grasslands in the study area is very low due to the degradation of the grassy carpet.

Keywords: *Leaota and Bucegi Mountains; permanent grasslands; pastoral value; milk production.*

INTRODUCTION

The vegetation of permanent grasslands in Romania has been studied and classified according to various geobotanical methods, especially the phytosociological one, with little or no data on forage production and quality (Anghel et al. 1971).

A first synthesis work with data on grassland production and quality was carried out in the period 1950-1960, when numerous changes in floristic composition and productivity occurred (Pușcaru-Soroceanu et al. 1963), making it necessary to renew the data.

Along with the inventory and mapping of permanent grasslands, the data regarding the productivity are necessary for drawing up pastoral arrangement projects (Marușca et al. 2014).

The main components of grasslands productivity are green mass production and forage quality that can be determined directly by weighing in protected areas and laboratory analysis or indirectly by assessment based on floristic survey (Marușca 2019).

The first direct method of determination is the most accurate but requires very high expenses and is sometimes almost impossible to apply due to the protection of fenced spaces on large and very extensive land areas.

The second method of evaluating productivity based on floristic composition is sufficiently accurate for drawing up a pastoral arrangement.

In addition, studies of the dynamics of grassland productivity can be done based on older floristic surveys compared to the current ones.

Our specialized literature abounds with geobotanical studies with the classification of the vegetation of permanent meadows that can still be used to evaluate their productivity (Puşcaru-Soroceanu et al. 1963; Anghel et al. 1971).

In the period 2019-2022, 33 mountains in the Romanian Carpathians and 19 locations in the area of hills and plains were taken into analysis and synthesis in a first approximation (Marușca 2022a,b).

The present paper is a continuation of this assessment action to know more precisely the past and present potential of our grasslands, based on floristic surveys to complete the economic data necessary for the development of mountain grasslands and the optimal management of this national asset.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The present study is based on the doctoral thesis entitled “*Flora and vegetation of the Leaota Mountains and the western slope of the Bucegi Mountains*” prepared by biologist Monica Neblea under the guidance of Nicolae Boscaiu and Aurelia Brezeanu, defended in 2007 at the Institute of Biology of the Romanian Academy, Bucharest.

The method of studying the grassland vegetation was the geobotanical one on the itinerary (Anghel et al. 1971).

The overview of plant associations of grasslands in the studied territory was as follows:

Cl. JUNCETEA TRIFIDI Klika et Hadač 1944

Ord. *Caricetalia curvulae* Br-Bl. 1926

Al. *Caricion curvulae* Br-Bl. 1926

1. As. *Oreochloo-Juncetum trifidi* Szafer et al.1927

2. As. *Potentillo chrysocraspedae - Festucetum airoidis* Boşcaiu 1971

3. As. *Cetrario - Loiseleurietum procumbentis* Br-Bl. et al.1939

Cl. NARDO CALLUNETEA Prsg.1949

Ord. *NARDETALIA* Oberd 1949

Al. *Potentillo - Nardion* Simon 1939

4. As. *Scorzonero roseae - Festucetum nigricantis* (Puşcaru et al.1956), Coldea 1978

5. As. *Violo declinatae - Nardetum strictae* Simon 1966

Cl. SESLERIETEA ALBICANTIS Br - Bl. Em. Oberd 1978

Ord. *SESLERIETALIA ALBICANTIS* Br - Bl. 1926

Al. *Festuco sextatilis-Seslerion bielzii* (Pawl.etWalas 1949)Coldea 1984

6. As. *Seslerio haynaldiana-Caricetum sempervirentis* Puşcaru et al.1956

7. As. *Asperulo capitatae-Seslerietum rigidae* (Zólyomi 1939) Coldea 1991

Cl. **MOLINIO-ARRHENATHERETEA** R. Tx.1937 em. R.Tx. 1970

Ord. *MOLINIETALIA* Koch 1926

Al. **Calthion** R.Tx 1937 em. Bal-Tul. 1978

8. As. *Scirpetum sylvatici* Ralski 1931 em. Schwich 1944; Deschampsion Horvatič 1930

Al. **Deschampsion** Horvatič 1930

9. As. *Deschampsietum caespitosae* Horvatič 1930

The proper working method for evaluating the grasslands productivity was presented in previous papers (Marușca et al. 2020, 2022) and more extensively in other accessible papers (Marușca 2019, 2023; Marușca et al. 2021), so it doesn't fall back on them.

In addition to evaluating the carpet productivity of permanent grasslands based on results in long-term experiences, it was possible to evaluate the production of cow's milk per hectare based on the pastoral value (Marușca et al. 2018).

The conversion coefficients (MCC) in possible cow milk production per hectare based on the index of pastoral value (PV) according to the altitude and the duration of the grazing season are shown in table 1.

Table 1. The milk conversion coefficient

Altitude (m)	Duration of grazing season (days)	Milk conversion coefficient
2000 - 2200	55	35
1800 - 2000	70	44
1600 - 1800	85	53
1400 - 1600	100	62
1200 - 1400	115	71
1000 - 1200	130	80
800 - 1000	145	89
600 - 800	160	98
400 - 600	175	107
Gradients for 100 m	- 7,5 days	- 4,5

In this case, the formula applies:

$$\text{Milk production (L/ha)} = \text{PV} \times \text{MCC}$$

This result is important for establishing the economic efficiency of animal production possible to achieve in the mountain area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The 78 grasslands floristic surveys were analysed, located at 700 - 2130 m altitude on mostly sunny exposures, on steep slopes (Table 2).

Table 2. General data on the season and vegetation of practical phytocenoses

No.	Vegetal association	No. survey	Altitude (m)	Exposure	Slope (degrees)	Cormophytes (no.)	Cover %
Al. <i>Caricion curvulae</i>							
1	<i>Oreochloa-juncetum trifidi</i>	5	2000 (1800-2130)	V,S,N	17(10-25)	29	54
2	<i>Potentillo chrysocraspedae - Festucetum airoidis</i>	12	1758 (1600-1900)	E,V,N,SE,NE	18(10-30)	39	79
3	<i>Cetrario - Loiseleurietum procumbentis</i>	5	2130	S.V.N	20 (10-35)	26	71
Al. <i>Potentillo - Nardion</i>							
4	<i>Scorzonero roseae - Festucetum nigricantis</i>	12	1691 (1400-1850)	Plan,S,E,SE,N,V	15 (5-30)	49	73
5	<i>Viola declinatae - Nardetum strictae</i>	13	1820 (1600-2130)	S,V,E,N	23(10-35)	43	91
Al. <i>Festuco saxatilis-Seslerion bielzii</i>							
6	<i>Seslerio haynaldianae-Cericetum sempervirentis</i>	5	1900	S,SE	52 (40-60)	34	74
7	<i>Asperulo capitatae-Seslerietum rigidae</i>	11	1109 (700-1500)	V,E,NE,NV,SV	83(70-90)	84	69
Al. <i>Calthion</i>							
8	<i>Scirpetum sylvatici</i>	5	900	N,NE,NV	6 (5-10)	39	82
Al. <i>Deschampsion</i>							
9	<i>Deschampsietum caespitosae</i>	10	1470 (1300-1500)	Plan, V,NE	9(0-25)	48	93
	TOTAL AVERAGE	76	1640 (700-2130)	ALL	27 (0--90)	44	76

The vegetation cover of 76% is considered quite low, with variations from 54-69% for *Oreochloo - Juncetum trifidi* associations to 91-93% for *Violo declinatae-Nardetum strictae* and *Deschampsietum caespitosae*.

In the grassy carpet of the associations, an average of 44 species of cormophytes were recorded, from 26 for *Cetrario - Loiseleurietum procumbentis* to 84 species in the *Asperulo capitatae-Seslerietum rigidae* association on the cliffs.

Regarding the participation in the grassy carpet of species with forrage value, it is found to be 31%, quite low with variations from 2% for *Violo declinatae-Nardetum strictae* and *Scirpetum sylvatici*, up to 54% for *Scorzonero roseae-Festucetum nigricantis* and 71 % in *Seslerio haynaldiana-Caricetum sempervirentis* (Table 3).

Table 3. Forage species participation, green mass production and pastoral value of meadow phytocenoses

No.	Grassland Association	Species structure (%)		Green Mass		Pastoral value		Appreciation
		Forager	Harmful	t/ha	%	ind.	%	
Al. <i>Caricion curvulae</i>								
1	<i>Oreochloo-Juncetum trifidi</i>	45	9	0,95	51	20,7	82	poor
2	<i>Potentillo chrysocraspedae - Festucetum airoidis</i>	43	36	0,91	49	24,4	96	poor
3	<i>Cetrario - Loiseleurietum procumbentis</i>	3	68	1,74	93	67,6	267	Good
Al. <i>Potentillo - Nardion</i>								
4	<i>Scorzonero roseae-Festucetum nigricantis</i>	54	19	7,52	405	41,2	163	medium
5	<i>Violo declinatae-Nardetum strictae</i>	2	89	0,10	5	1,0	4	degraded
Al. <i>Festuco saxatilis-Seslerion bielzii</i>								
6	<i>Seslerio haynaldiana-Caricetum sempervirentis</i>	71	3	2,85	152	37,5	148	degraded
7	<i>Asperulo capitatae-Seslerietum rigidae</i>	52	17	2,08	11	28,3	112	degraded
Al. <i>Calthion</i>								
8	<i>Scirpetum sylvatici</i>	80	2	0,16	9	1,2	5	degraded
Al. <i>Deschampsion</i>								
9	<i>Deschampsietum caespitosae</i>	6	87	0,54	29	4,2	17	degraded
Average		40	36	1,87	100	25,3	100	mediocre

The participation degree in the grassy carpet of forage species has a direct influence on the grassland's productivity.

On average, the production of 1.69 t/ha green mass is considered very low.

Better production results were evaluated in the associations *Scorzonero roseae-Festucetum nigricantis* (7.52 t/ha), *Seslerio haynaldianae - Caricetum sempervirentis* (2.85 t/ha) and *Asperulo capitatae-Seslerietum rigidae* (2.08 t/ha) in the rest all the other 6 associations have less than 1 t/ha of green mass.

The pastoral value is also very low, averaging 17.8 with variations from 1.2 (degraded) for *Scirpetum syvatici*, to 41.2 (average) for the most valuable *Scorzonero roseae-Festucetum nigricantis* association.

In the Stânișoara Mountains of the Eastern Carpathians, the pastoral value of the *Scorzonero roseae-Festucetum nigricantis* association was 57.2, 40% higher and a green mass production of 9 t/ha, 20% higher than the Leaota - Bucegi Mountains. (Marușca et al. 2021).

The final grassland productivity used by grazing is expressed by animal production as gain in live weight, milk, wool, etc.

In this study the production of cow's milk was evaluated which is on average 1020 liters per hectare (Table 4).

Table 4. Optimum animal loading, length of grazing season and cow milk production of phytosociological orders

The phytosociological order	Green mass production		Duration of grazing season (days)	Optimal loading LU/ha	Pastoral value (ind)	Milk production	
	t/ha	%				liter/ha	%
<i>Caricetalia</i>	0,95	36	75	0,13	15,6	730	72
<i>Nardetalia</i>	3,81	209	85	0,69	21,1	1110	109
<i>Seslerietalia</i>	2,48	136	100	0,41	32,9	2040	200
<i>Molinietalia</i>	0,35	19	120	0,04	2,7	200	20
Average	1,82	100	95	0,29	18,1	1020	100

The highest milk production was evaluated in phytocoenoses belonging to the order *Seslerietalia* of 2040 L/ha and the lowest in those of the order *Molinietalia* 200 L/ha, which is composed of two forage-dependent associations, *Scirpetum syvatici*, and *Deschampsietum caespitosae* with 80-89% participation harmful, worthless species.

Very low milk productions on the degraded grasslands of the Semenicului Mountains, invaded by *Nardus stricta*, *Deschampsia caespitosa* and other weeds, were recorded in the practical alliance (habitat) *Potentilla - Nardion*, 350 liters of milk per hectare (Marușca et al. 2023).

In general, the grasslands productivity in Leaota and the west of the Bucegi Mountains is lower than in other mountain massifs.

CONCLUSION

- The permanent grasslands of Leaota Mountains - west Bucegi located at 700 - 2130 m altitude have a phytodiversity of 44 cormophyte species in an association, being quite high for the conditions in the high mountains;
- The association with the most cormophyte species was *Asperula capitata - Seslerietum rigidae* (84 sp) and with the fewest Cetrario - Loiselierietum procumbentis (29 sp);
- The grassland productivity used for grazing is very low with 18 index of pastoral value and 1.8 t/ha green fodder mass from which a little over 1000 liters of milk per hectare can be obtained in 95 days grazing season with a load of 0, 29 LU/ha;
- The highest milk production of 2040 liters/ha was evaluated in the phytocenoses belonging to the order *Seslerietalia*, with an index of 33 pastoral value, a production of 2.48 t / ha green mass and a load of 0.41 LU/ha in 100 days of grazing season;
- The lowest milk production of 200 l/ha was in the order *Molinietalia* with almost 3 pastoral value, production of 0.35 t/ha green mass, a load of 0.04 LU/ha in 120 days of possible grazing season.
- After the inventory and mapping of the vegetation necessary for the preparation of the pastoral arrangements, the economic data regarding the assessment of the pastoral value and the production of green mass and milk, will continue to serve us in the optimal management of these mountain grasslands.

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